

REDUCED ORAL BACTERIAL DIVERSITY LINKED TO ORAL CANCER RECURRENCE AND TUMOR GRADE

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Background/ Introduction:

The oral microbiota, a community of mouth microorganisms, could be a valuable indicator for oral cancer. Research suggests differences in salivary microbiome composition between healthy individuals and oral cancer patients, making it a potential biomarker. Next-generation sequencing of biological samples like saliva, oral cavity swabs, and tumor tissue from OSCC patients and healthy controls is an emerging technique.

Given the high prevalence of head and neck cancer in Kamrup, Assam as per National Cancer Registry Programme (NCRP), we were interested in exploring unique microbial signatures in OSCC patients. We selected 13 subjects: 5 with high-grade tumor/relapse (G1), 5 with low-grade tumor/remission (G2), and 3 healthy controls (G3). We performed 16S rRNA metagenome sequencing on these subjects.

Objectives

A cohort of 13 subjects was recruited from KaviKrishna Telemedicine (a division of KKL) following informed written consent and assigned to groups G1, G2, and G3. The primary objective of this study was to determine the prevalence, composition, and diversity of oral bacteria in oral saliva of the subjects. By analysing the microbial profiles, we sought to establish a link between bacterial signatures and patient pathobiology.

Materials and Methods

We collected morning saliva samples from the patients and extracted DNA using phenol chloroform DNA isolation method. 3ng of DNA was used to amplify V3-V4 region and 16S rRNA sequencing was performed. The raw data was obtained and analysed for abundance of bacteria in the groups, alpha diversity, beta diversity rarefaction curve and PCA plot of the samples.

Results and Conclusions

We identified seven major bacterial phyla across all groups (G1, G2, and G3). However, G1 showed a distinct microbial profile with a dominance of a few phyla, while G2 and G3 had a more balanced distribution. This pattern persisted at the genus and species levels. Certain bacteria, like *Prevotella melaninogenica*, were more abundant across all groups. Rarefaction

curve analysis revealed a decreasing trend in bacterial diversity from G3 to G1. This suggests that G1 had the lowest microbial diversity, while G3 had the highest. Alpha diversity indices, including richness and evenness, revealed that G1 was the least diverse group compared to G2 and G3. This study highlights the potential role of oral bacterial diversity in the development and progression of OSCC. Reduced bacterial diversity, particularly in high-grade tumor and relapse cases, may contribute to disease severity.

Ethics statement: This study was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee of KaviKrishna Laboratory, and Thoreau Laboratory for Global Health, M2D2, University of Massachusetts, Lowell, MA, USA, KaviKrishna Telemedicine Care, Sualkuchi. Necessary patient consent was taken as per guidelines of the Institutional Ethics Committee of KaviKrishna Laboratory, IIT Guwahati Research Park, Indian Institute of Technology, Guwahati, India.